

To Study the Patient Waiting Time versus the Level of Satisfaction at Holy Family Hospital (Hfh), Rawalpindi

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Abstract:

OPD is a window to hospital services and satisfaction of health consumers is related with patients expectations and their actual experiences¹. Patient's satisfaction is a critical issue for health providers working in a competitive environment with other hospitals can be improved if patients expectation is met and waiting time is reduced coupled with a sound healthcare service²

1. Introduction

A patient's impression of hospital begins at OPD and it is well established that 8-10% of OPD patients need hospitalization. A well-managed, neat and clean hospital with necessary information boards and proper directions generally provide good image. Successful and efficient management of OPD can also lighten the burden on the patient wards.⁴

It's a usual sight in a developing countries like Pakistan to see a large number of chronically ill and undiagnosed patients waiting in a long queue in the outpatient departments of the hospitals who on an average require longer doctor's consultation time. Lengthy consultation times has a backlog effect on clinic waiting time⁵. There are quite a few studies from Pakistan⁶ about measuring the patient satisfaction in different domains like in-patient, day case surgery satisfaction⁷ but limited local data is available about patient experiences from Out Patients Department (OPD) and their satisfaction.

In the present study effort is being done to find out the satisfaction level of patients waiting for the consultation with the doctor in the OPD of the Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi. Behavior of the doctor while examining the patient for an optimum time to the satisfaction of client is also in the purview of the study.

2. Objectives

1. To determine the patient waiting time.
2. To study the satisfaction level of patients on examination by doctor.

3. Operational Definitions

Outpatient Department (OPD):

OPD is defined as the hospital's department where patients received diagnoses and/or treatment but did not stay overnight.⁸

Patients' Waiting Time:

Defined as, "the length of time from when the patient enters the out-patient clinic to the time patient actually leaves the OPD".⁸

4. Material and Methods

Study design:	Descriptive study
Study population:	Patients attending OPD of Holy Family Hospital, Rawalpindi.
Study site:	Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi.
Sample size:	264
Sampling technique:	Convenient sampling
Inclusion Criteria:	All patients visiting OPD of HFH
Exclusion Criteria:	Infants going for Vaccination, Patients referred to Casualty, Patients going for dialysis.
Data collection tool:	Self structured questionnaires
Data analysis:	SPSS – 20. Likert Scale of Rating
Study duration:	15 days

5. Work Plan

Topic discussion and questionnaire development

1 day

Data Collection

3 days

Data entry

2 days

Analysis and results

2 days

Compilation of work

2 days

6. Ethical consideration

- Informed consent was taken from the participants.
- Anonymity of respondents was ensured.

7. Results

Table 1. Age Statistics

Total	264
Mean	32.3674
Std. Deviation	11.97294
Range	61.00
Minimum	9.00
Maximum	70.00

Figure 1. Gender

Figure 2. Address

Figure 3. Socioeconomic

Figure 4. Education

Figure 7. Time in Doctor's waiting

Figure 5. Time in reaching the Required hospital OPD

Figure 8. Time consumed in Doctor's Consultation

Figure 6. Time in getting the opd ticket

Figure 9. Satisfaction with time spent in doctor waiting

Figure 10. Level of cleanliness

Figure 11. Satisfaction with temperature in sitting Area

Figure 12. Satisfaction with sitting arrangements

Figure 13. Satisfaction with time consumed with doctor

Figure 14. Satisfaction with doctor behavior

Total	264
Mean	6.613
Std. Deviation	1.65296
Range	6.00
Minimum	3.00
Maximum	9.00

Table 2. Waiting Time

Total	264
Mean	11.7576
Std. Deviation	4.11825

Range	28.00
Minimum	5.00
Maximum	3.00

Table 3. Satisfaction statistics

Figure 15. Satisfaction with time consumed with doctor

5. Discussion

In our study the mean age of patients came out to be 32.37 ± 11.97 years with 70% females. In another study the mean age of patient attending the OPD was 30.31 ± 15.65 years, of which female patients are more (54.07%) than the male patient (45.93%)⁹. Similar finding was noted by a Kolade J Obamiro in his study at Nigeria that majority of patients were female (65%) dominated with patients of 18 to 24 ages (45%)¹⁰. Umar I et al in their study noted that 45% of the respondents were males while there were 55% females and ages of the respondents ranged from 20 to 72 years with a mean age of 38 years which was low compared to the mean age of 45 years obtained in a similar study in Karachi, Pakistan.^{11,12}

Reasoning to this finding is that mostly males in the day time are on work places and moreover gynae and paed opd are feminine show. In our study 20% patients were illiterate, 23% educated up to primary level, 32% did matriculation, 10% claimed for FSc and just 14% were graduate and above. Sharma A et al noted that 22% of patients were graduate and above followed by primary education (26%), higher secondary education (20%), middle school (18%) and illiterate (14%)¹³

The level of education definitely effects the searching of various departments in the hospital and increases waiting time. The mean waiting time of our study came out to be 6.6 ± 1.65 minutes which is lesser as compared to another study which was

12.16 ± 2.35 minutes⁹. This may be attributed to better waiting time management of administration of HFH.

According to standard operating procedures of OPD for district level hospitals waiting time for collection of OPD ticket is one minute. In comparison to these standards waiting time, the findings of this study showed that it is rather longer¹⁴. The study shows that 32.30 % patients have a consultation time up to 5 minutes, 43.56 % for 6-10 minutes and rest of 24.24 % receive 11-12 minutes for their ailments, in comparison Sharma A et al found that 56% were examined for Less than 5 min, 34% were examined for 5-15 min, 4% examined for 15-30 min and 6% were examined more than 30 min¹³. Our study participants receive more attention by doctor due to availability of more staff placed in OPD according to the patients burden.

Our study shows as the waiting time is going to increase, satisfaction level is going to drop. Nandkeshav AR et al found significant statistical association between less waiting time and satisfaction expressed about OPD services¹⁵.

6. Conclusion

As the waiting time increases satisfaction level with hospital OPD services decreases.

Majority of the Patients are satisfied with the behavior of the doctors and services available at the OPD of HFH.

7. Limitations

1. Time was limited.
2. Language barrier.

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